

Multi-criteria Knowledge-based decision-making functionality for swarm of drones

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Abstract—Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), or commonly referred to as drones are now being utilized for a variety of data-intensive applications in the transportation civil and military sectors, in a way that has never occurred before. The UAV swarm system, which refers to a cooperative formation of UAVs that conduct exploration and mapping activities in a synergistic mode, is part of the most well-known new scenarios that have been introduced in recent years. A significant challenge of such systems is determining the kind of UAV swarm architecture that will enable increased efficiency and resilience in operations. This study suggests a framework for energy efficient and robust swarm missions that relies on a decision-based functionality for the actions of each entity in the swarm for various mission scenarios, while numerical results showcase the efficiency of our proposed method. Finally, comprehensive simulation results based on a custom-developed simulator showcase the effectiveness, scalability, and applicability of the proposed model.

Index Terms—UAV swarms, swarm intelligence, energy management, trajectory optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) are recently becoming pivotal due to their autonomous nature, fast and flexible deployment, and high mobility, while recent technology advancements in sensors and communication technologies have opened the way for new applications that will further boost their use. This has led to a growing interest among business leaders, policymakers, and the public and has created more business opportunities. With a constantly evolving market potential in various segments, it is expected that the drone services market in Europe will grow exponentially (1).

The use of UAVs brings great advantages, such as extended autonomy, high mobility, safety, and economic value, and opens the way for a huge area of commercial opportunities (2). Particularly Beyond Visual Line Of Sight (BVLOS) operations have gained significant attention in recent years, as they endow flights with several degrees of intelligence and efficiency, a lower cost, and a reduced risk to human life (3). However, despite their inherent advantages, BVLOS sets a number of complex requirements for the operation of UAVs due to their unpredictable dynamics, limited onboard energy resources, security and safety concerns of flights, and an unclear regulatory framework

To tackle the complexity of BVLOS missions, new emerging scenarios have been introduced in recent years. Among them is the use of collaborative UAVs. Inspired by the natural formations of creatures, such as the flock of birds or the schools of fish, a UAV swarm consists of a number of

aircrafts with restricted autonomy and communication ability that operate together in a synergistic mode in order to perform cooperative exploration and mapping tasks, such as data collection, path planning, or co-mapping generation and validation (2; 4).

However, the emergence of more challenging operational scenarios in recent years has introduced new challenges that impede the wider adoption of UAV swarms. In this work, we aim to address the problem of efficient mission scheduling of UAV swarms in challenging and diverse environments. The contributions of this work can be summarized in the following:

- A complete UAV swarms ecosystem, comprising a group of cellular-connected UAVs that cooperate in order to achieve trajectory optimization and efficient energy management.
- A decision-based functionality that defines the actions of each entity in the swarm based on a traveling salesman problem (TSP) modeling based on integer linear programming.
- An implementation that considers two diverse and representative scenarios for UAV missions, namely coverage, and surveillance.

In Section II that follows we perform an overview of related works on UAV swarms implementations. Section III provides the details of the proposed simulation model and implementation environment for UAV swarm actions as well as the energy consumption models. Section IV explains the experimental setup, the simulated scenarios, as well as the numerical results of our simulations. Finally, Section V concludes the paper and sets the scene for future steps in this field.

II. RELATED WORK

The ecosystem of UAV swarm systems is taking a pivotal role in various sophisticated operational scenarios in recent years (5). Through their swarm intelligence mechanism, these autonomous clusters can perform tasks with greater efficiency, and lower risks, by breaking them into several simple sub-tasks (6). Despite their inherent advantages and distributed nature, the coordination of multiple UAVs in the sky still hinders several challenges. In UAV swarm systems the type of structure that will facilitate greater efficiency and robustness to multiple unmanned platforms is the first problem to be tackled. This problem may often involve the collaboration of heterogeneous devices, such as UAVs, or Ground Control Stations (GCS) with different communication infrastructures,

coordination strategies, control mechanisms, or mission planning algorithms.

A number of recent works have focused on improving the performance and robustness of the deployment of UAV swarms by exploring different formation strategies and architectures. An interesting work (7) proposed a joint trajectory and resource allocation algorithm design for solar-powered UAVs for maximizing the system sum throughput. Their model considered the aerodynamic power consumption, the solar energy harvesting, the finite onboard energy storage, and the minimum QoS requirements of the users. The artificial potential field (APF) method has been proposed in (8; 9) to achieve the generation and maintenance of the desired formation shape for a UAV swarm. Optimization-based approaches have also been explored. Such methods consider the assumption that an objective function aims to minimize or maximize certain constraints according to a set of criteria. Some recent works on optimization-based formation control are proposed by (10; 11). Another widespread UAV swarm formation technique in literature is the leader–follower configuration. According to this method, one entity of the swarm is assigned as the leader, and the rest of the followers are bound to adjust their position with respect to the leader’s path (12).

To our knowledge, previous works examine UAV swarm systems issues distinctively and not as a whole. In our work, we propose a swarm intelligence model of UAVs that work cooperatively in order to determine the best possible action in their environment, with respect to energy efficiency and optimal trajectory generation. The algorithmic design is based on an integer linear programming problem modeling, while as opposed to previous works, our methodology extends to diverse use cases, such as surveillance and coverage.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

For our experiments we employed a simulation environment which can be a reliable and efficient way for testing and validating the performance of our UAV swarm algorithms. In this section, we present the simulation model and showcase the distinct activities and in which cases an action is applicable. We assume that the proposed model considers a total of 4 swarms with a group multitude $N = 3$. All entities have a predefined limit for battery capacity, which prohibits them from performing an action and immediately forces the whole swarm to land at the closest charging positions. Furthermore, all the UAVs used in this simulation are of the same type, with multiple rotors, capable of vertical take-off and landing for simplicity. In the next steps of our work, we will address important requirements regarding the type of UAVs, and we plan to examine various setups.

A. Simulation Environment

The simulation environment constitutes a three-dimensional multicell 5G flying ad hoc network (FANET). The basic elements of our environment are shown in Fig. ???. The cells are dictated using the Voronoi Tessellation (13) and can be referred to as places. These places are divided into two categories *sites*

and *areas*. A site contains a central GCS, charging positions for the multitude of UAVs and for the duration that a UAV is situated in such a place it remains landed on the ground. The multitude of sites S equals two, whereas the total number of places $P = 20$. Out of those places are the remaining areas, where an area includes only cellular users and the swarm aims to pass through all areas and monitor or provide coverage to them for at least a single time interval. During the flight, the swarm will move through the areas executing the predefined missions until the battery capacity of at least one of the UAV members is less than a preset minimum threshold.

A single point is formed utilizing the three axes and in the case of the individual UAV $_i(x_i, y_i, z_i)$, where $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$. These sets are different for every UAV during flight mode. At the start of a mission the UAVs are stationary within a site on the ground, so their altitude is $h_i = 0$. When the swarm takes off, it will reach a specific altitude and maintain it for the remainder of the mission. The execution of this operation is carried out in the length of a day, divided into time slots signifying 10 minutes. This time frame can be marked as TS and a time interval is $t \in \{1, \dots, TS\}$.

During this time frame, the swarms are capable of carrying out two separate missions, a surveillance mission, and a coverage mission. For surveillance, the swarm monitors an area utilizing an onboard camera for a specified time slot, whereas for coverage a UAV carries a Low-Level (LL) functional base station and provides downlink (DL) signals to ground terminals. In this work, we test the energy efficiency and consumption of specific actions when the swarms are operating.

B. UAV Actions

In the following, we will focus on the feasible activities that an individual UAV can perform in this system and how it determines the actions for every time interval. It is important to stress that distinct UAV actions can be performed in different places. Also, an action is executed collectively using the concept of a leader. The leader of the swarm communicates with the remaining members of the group and decides the course of action.

At the beginning of every time slot, the leader informs the group about the activity and the next positions. When a swarm is located inside a site it has the following options:

- (A) *STAY*: The UAVs of the group will reside for the duration of a time slot on the ground and won’t consume any amount of energy.
- (B) *REC*: The UAVs are connected to the recharging stations and can fully replenish their battery capacity in an hour.
- (C) *ASC*: The group raises from the ground to a predefined altitude while moving from a site to an area.

Nonetheless, in the case where the swarm is located over the areas, then it is capable of:

- (A) *SURV*: In a surveillance action the swarm collects data exploiting an on board-camera and at the end of the time slot it transmits them to the closest GCS for further pro-

Fig. 1. An example of the coverage action when it is applicable. $z_i, i = 1, \dots, 20$ are the areas to visits, $s_j, j = 1, 2$ are the base/charging points and the star markers denote the cellular users. Hexagons are the UAVs and diamonds are the base stations. The dark magenta denotes the leader of the swarm

cessing. For this action, the UAVs retain their positions and remain stationary over the corresponding area.

- (B) *MOVE*: The UAVs move through areas in regard to the path dictated solely for the leader. The remaining members of the swarm are always placed in the adjacent areas of the leader. This action can exclusively occur after the surveillance action has been completed at least once.
- (C) *HOV*: This action is excluded from selection and will only be forced to a UAV if its current position happens to be one of the next positions based on the path. Then, the individual UAV will not move to another area and instead hover. However, this can also occur in the case of a coverage mission, when a COV action is chosen but no CUEs are present in the vicinity of the relevant area.
- (D) *COV*: Only during a coverage mission this action is feasible. Through the concept of multicast each UAV in the swarm delivers coverage to a multitude of cellular ground users in the relevant area. Throughout this activity, a UAV will not move. Figure 1 showcases how the program portrays this action.
- (E) *DESC*: In the descent operation, the swarm lands on the ground, transporting from an area to a site. This step can be taken voluntarily or when at least one member of the swarm has to recharge their battery due to low energy capacity.

We assume that the leader of the swarm is determined during the first ASC. The model randomly selects an area for each of the three members of a swarm and calculates the distances. The leader is decided to be the UAV assigned with the smallest distance from the site and will stay the same until

another ASC is executed. Moreover, when the swarm has to be swapped while on flight, the next group will rise to the positions, in order to maintain continuity through the mission. Once a mission is completed, meaning the swarms have passed from all areas, the last swarm performs the DESC action and then a new mission can be initialized.

C. Energy Consumption Models

In this subsection, we will briefly describe the energy consumption with every applicable action. We assume that all UAVs move with a steady velocity through the 3D environment. The energy consumption model for the ASC, DESC, and MOVE acts is examined first. To begin, we calculate the total mass of the UAV, which varies depending on the type of operation due to the payload that each individual must transport. The intended altitude difference during transportation has a significant impact on actions like ASC/DESC. The travel time to reach the predefined altitude is measured as, $dt_{ver} = \frac{h_i}{v_{ver}}$, where h_i is the altitude to reach and v_{ver} is the vertical velocity. The same process is applied to the horizontal flight time. As total travel time tends to be lower than the duration of a time slot each UAV will hover for the remaining time. The energy cost for hovering in Joules is given by:

$$E_{Hov} = \frac{W^{3/2}}{\sqrt{2r\rho\alpha}}. \quad (1)$$

Here $W = mg$, where m is the overall mass, and we assume that airspeed and weight forces are balanced by the propulsion (14). In addition r is the number of rotors of the drone, ρ is

the air density and lastly α is the rotor disk area. The vertical energy cost is calculated using the formula:

$$E_v(\delta_t) = W \cdot (v_{ver}) \cdot dt_{ver}. \quad (2)$$

The energy required for horizontal motion during steady flight is represented by the symbol E_h and is influenced by a wide range of variables. It can be represented as a linear sum of the minimal energy needed to keep the UAV in the air for steady flight, the energy consumed for vertical flight, and the drag profile of the blades, as depicted in (7).

$$E_h(\delta_t) = \frac{\delta_t}{\sqrt{V_h(\delta_t)^2 + \sqrt{V_h(\delta_t)^4 + 4 \cdot E_{hover}(\delta_t)^4}} \cdot \frac{(W)^2}{\sqrt{2} \cdot \rho \cdot \alpha}. \quad (3)$$

where V_h is the horizontal velocity, and E_{hover} signifies the minimum energy for the drone to stay in the air. Consequently, $E_{hover} = \sqrt{\frac{W}{2\rho\alpha}}$. The action's duration is indicated by δt , although for calculating purposes, $\delta t = dt_{hor}$. It is also important to note that this model is affected by the drag profile of the UAV (resistance from the air to the aircraft blades) and the total resistance energy for a time interval is calculated by:

$$E_{res}(\delta_t) = \frac{1}{8} \cdot d_r \cdot \rho \cdot \alpha \cdot V_h(\delta_t)^3 \cdot \delta_t \quad (4)$$

where d_r signifies a drag profile coefficient, dependent on the geometry of the rotor blades. After calculating the aerodynamic model, the drag profile, and the vertical energy cost, we can unite these elements and measure the energy consumption for the ASC, DESC, and MOVE actions with small dissimilarities in the final models. Regarding ASC the formula is:

$$E_{asc}(\delta_t) = E_h(\delta_t) + E_v(\delta_t) + E_{res}(\delta_t). \quad (5)$$

The same stands for the DESC activity. However, the main contrast lies in the vertical energy, which depending on the direction of flight in relation to the gravitational acceleration direction the value can be positive or negative. In other words, the ascension will always be more energy intensive than the descent. In the case of the MOVE activity the vertical energy cost is disregarded and so the formula is $E_{move}(\delta_t) = E_h(\delta_t) + E_{res}(\delta_t)$. Nevertheless, as aforementioned, a UAV will perform the decided action and almost always complete it before the time slot is finished. For the remaining available time the UAV will hover, retaining its position in the air, therefore the overall energy consumption for the entire action is $E_{Asc}(Wh) = E_{asc}(J) + E_{Hov}(W)$ and in a similar manner for DESC and MOVE.

A drone will execute one of the subsequent stationary activities, SURV or COV, when it arrives over an area. The drone is required to lift and carry a common portable surveillance camera or a LL base station depending on the mission type. We presume that a drone is capable of lifting only one payload

during flight. The energy used for surveillance is formulated as:

$$E_{surv}(\delta_t) = (\beta + \alpha \cdot h_i) \cdot (\delta_t) + P_{h_i} \quad (6)$$

This empirical analysis of energy usage makes use of actual measurements from UAV suppliers and electrical motors. In the equation β stands for the minimal amount of power required to hover over the ground, α is the motor speed multiplier for the amount of power required to ascend to altitude h_i and P_{h_i} is a constant to regulate the amount of power required to lift the UAV off the ground and to a particular height. In order to retain basic surveillance functions for the camera throughout a given time frame, we integrate P_{cam} (15). So, $E_{Surv} = E_{surv} + P_{cam}$. Lastly for the COV action, with a maximum multitude of cellular users, M , for each separate area, we assume that multicasting is applicable and may be engaged using a LL base station mounted on the UAV. The amount of energy needed to cover an area for a short period of time is:

$$E_{Cov}(\delta_t) = E_{Surv}(\delta_t) + P_{UBS} \cdot \delta_t, \quad (7)$$

where the energy required for the base station to multicast to several ground terminals is P_{UBS} and it is the minimum power for low-level operations according to (16).

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Setup

All simulations are executed in MATLAB R2020, in a Dell system with Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-8250U CPU @ 1.80GHz. To assess the efficiency of our proposed algorithm with regard to energy and trajectory optimization, we perform a comparative analysis of two respective scenarios, with and without our algorithm implementation. Moreover, we assume that each entity in the swarm of UAVs will only have to go through an area once, which ensures that the system will complete a single mission in a finite time frame. Moreover, we consider that scenario changes with the mission type.

B. Scenarios

Our system considers two distinct mission types for the swarms, influencing the actions a group will execute. The simulations always start with the surveillance mission and when a mission ends the mission type swaps. Furthermore, we opted to combine the different missions with distinct path-planning algorithms. Specifically, our proposed model takes into account a normal simulation, meaning that the next position for the swarm is entirely randomly generated, though we must admit that with every area visited the pool of available areas decreases. To enhance our results we design a second scenario where we utilise the Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) algorithm, a very popular method for typical optimization problems. To this, we assess their ability to obtain optimal paths in terms of length and execution time. In both scenarios, path planning is occurring with regard to the leader of the group.

Fig. 2. The flow of actions for every UAV during TS in TSP simulation.

C. Numerical Results

Figure (2) indicates a full execution of the TSP scenario in the simulation environment, focusing on the actions which are unanimously performed by the UAVs of the swarm. The swarm will continuously execute different activities as long as the battery capacity of every member is above the minimum threshold P_{min} set to $P_{min} = 150$ Wh. Significantly, through the utilization of the TSP optimization, the UAVs will always act collaboratively performing the same action in every time interval as opposed to the normal simulation where an individual UAV will be forced to alter the action selected by the leader. Subsequently, even though the TSP simulation has significant performance and energy gains, the multitude of actions performed is approximately similar to normal execution, but when those deviations occur the normal execution spends a great amount of time and energy resources to catch up to the TSP method. During experimentation, there were cases that a swarm would perform 2-3 more actions per mission type due to the higher transportation demands in normal execution. This goes along with the steady energy cost of SURV and COV and the lower energy boundary set that is the same for both simulations. Finally it becomes clear that in a more realistic approach, a system using TSP will always pass through all areas in sequence and as a result the execution time will remain steady through instances. That is not the case however when the UAVs are let to decide in random the next area of action.

Figure 3 depicts the battery levels captured when each UAV begins its mission until it recharges. At first, it becomes clear that some UAVs would lose energy below the minimum predefined level, closing to zero, making it impossible for them to land normally. Based on numerical results, in a normal execution, the *Fail Rate (%)* could reach up to 3.8% whereas for TSP the at most upper limit was set to 2.52%. Clearly the lower the minimum energy is set, the more the failure rate increases. Secondly, when the swarms are switched, the new group practically never begins the execution with fully charged batteries. This happens as a result of the shift in locations during flight, with the ascent's energy cost accounting for approximately 130Wh. In other words, the UAVs are unable to

Fig. 3. The battery capacity for each individual UAV throughout a whole execution.

fully utilize their battery capabilities. Aside from the fact that the distribution of energy varies between executions due to previously stated reasons, a UAV might experience extremely high energy costs during a normal execution, requiring the group to preemptively swap.

Figure 4 depicts the main comparison as calculated with the mean energy consumption recorded during our experimentation phase. It is noticeable that there are no distinctions in relation to energy cost corresponding to STAY, SURV, and COV actions because the parameters affecting the calculation formulas are identical for the two scenarios. Moreover, the deviation observed for the ASC activity and in larger levels for DESC is ultimately influenced by the distance the swarm must cover to ascend or descend to the closest site and by the number of times these actions are performed. Nevertheless, the HOV and MOVE activities produced the most significant performance results. For HOV, the percentage difference between the two simulations ranges up to 13.7%, and for MOVE, it reaches 14.8%. That means that the energy consumption is significantly less when the TSP algorithm is enabled. The location that the swarm will occupy over the areas for the two mission types during a HOV action depends only on the path planning and it can be directly tied to the number of actions needed to execute a single mission.

Using the TSP algorithm to plan MOVE paths greatly minimizes the energy utilized as MOVE is performed the same number of times throughout all simulations. The shortest distance between two regions that TSP can determine enables the swarm to avoid wasting a lot of battery power traveling between the areas without order. TSP also greatly aids in more straightforwardly coordinating the UAVs. This is evident when considering that in a typical execution with random area selection, the drones visit the same areas repeatedly until all areas have been covered. However, in our simulations, this is not the case as mentioned because it will run for a very long time without making any noticeable progress. In conclusion, with TSP more missions are likely to be completed than with normal execution because this energy reduction allows for more actions to be performed by a swarm without losing time in swapping. When the randomization

Fig. 4. Comparison of average energy costs for both simulations.

aspect was eliminated from selecting the actions, meaning that the selection of actions was "forced", the TSP simulation completed an average of three missions as opposed to two during a typical normal execution.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Our proposed model examines the problem of resilient UAV swarm missions, by examining efficient the generation trajectories, and knowledge-based determination of action. The comparison between the normal execution and the TSP simulation indicates the importance of path planning in UAV deployed systems whereas the swarm concept provides increased coverage and larger portions monitored in a single time interval. Lastly, we proved the advantages of a path-planning algorithm in regard to the coordination of the group. For future work, we aspire to scale up this model, alter the optimization for path planning and try to establish this type of system for distinct elements such as autonomous ground vehicles and underwater unmanned vehicles and lastly to consider the impact of wireless communication latency and energy in leader-follower command and control communication.

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